

IMPACT OF MICRO TEACHING ON VOCATIONAL AND TECHNICAL EDUCATION STUDENT-TEACHERS' PERFORMANCE DURING TEACHING PRACTICE IN ABIA STATE

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ABSTRACT

The study was carried out to examine the impact of micro teaching, using Vocational and Technical Education student-teachers' performance during teaching practice in Abia State. The design of the study was descriptive survey. Three research questions and one null hypothesis were posed; tested at 0.05 level of significance. The target population consisted of 1345 Vocational and Technical Education students drafted from the 2 Public Universities in Abia state, Nigeria (i.e MOUAU and ABSU), while the sample size was 299 respondents determined using Yaro's Yamane Formula. A self-structured questionnaire titled: Micro teaching Impact Questionnaire (MTIQ) was developed, validated and used for the study. The internal consistency reliability of the instruments was determined using Cronbach Alpha procedure and reliability estimate of 0.82 was obtained for the MTIQ. The instrument was made up of a total of 27 content items, 9 items each in three sections. It adopted a four point modified type scale model of; 4 (Strongly Agreed), 3 (Agreed), 2 (Disagreed) and 1 (Strongly Disagreed). The questionnaires were administered by hand with the help of 7 trained research assistants and all the copies were returned. The data obtained from data collection were analyzed using mean and standard to answer the research questions and t-test for the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Based on the data collected and analyzed, there is a positive impact of micro teaching on Vocational and Technical education student-teachers' performance during teaching practice in Abia state. It was therefore recommended among others that since micro teaching is costly and expensive, adequate fund should be provided by government and appropriate sectors to facilitate the continuous development of micro teaching in faculties of education in Nigerian Universities.

Keywords: Micro Teaching, Teaching Practice, Students, Performance, Vocational and Technical Education

INTRODUCTION

Teaching is a multifaceted, intricate, and varied activity, and a teacher must be able to educate well in order to fulfill their duty. Effective teaching uses a variety of cognitive, emotive, and interpersonal elements, making it an intelligent knowledge-based activity. Thus, there is a need for high-quality training that can increase efficacy, and teacher education programs are the only way to obtain this. Programs for teacher training require proper practice. According to Obayan (2014),

teachers should possess sufficient teaching abilities in addition to subject-matter expertise. Effective teacher preparation is the most important attribute of a teacher, according to Ambili (2013). To improve teacher education, numerous innovations are implemented, such as computer-assisted instruction, simulated teaching, micro-teaching, and programmed instruction. As an innovation in teacher education, micro-teaching is frequently used to prepare pre-service teachers for research including the study of teaching and learning processes as well as for the acquisition of teaching abilities.

In the 1960s, Dwight Allen and a group of academics and researchers at Stanford University in California created the technique. In a controlled laboratory setting, it was mainly conducted to train student-teachers to develop a repertory of teaching techniques (Brown, 2015). This is to remove the difficulties of actual classroom instruction (class size, subject, time etc) and for practice of skills independently for acquisition. Since it is a highly customised form of teacher training, it is a useful tool for changing the behaviours of instructors undergoing training. Additionally, it helps instructors develop their competencies during pre-service and in-service teacher training (Rufai et al., 2013). According to Syed and Zaid (2018), microteaching is a procedure that stimulates the development of social skills and aims to give teachers feedback so they can change their behaviour. He comes to the conclusion that it is a clinical teaching programme designed to give teachers brief experiences. Microteaching as an essential part of formal education training for teachers has its objectives which include enabling teacher trainees gain confidence in teaching by mastering a number of skills on a smaller group of students; providing teacher-trainees with an environment for practice-based teaching and through this instil some self-evaluative skills.

Micro teaching helps student-teachers imbibe the qualities of effective teaching, avoid common mistakes made by teachers, and equip themselves with the necessary mastery skills and techniques of good teaching, microteaching is a field or branch of teacher education that is crucial for teachers in training, according to its objectives (Goodlad, 2010). Through microteaching, teacher candidates can hone their abilities to capture students' interest, pose questions, use and manage time efficiently, and wrap up the class. Additionally, microteaching helps teachers become more adept at managing their classes. They gain the ability to select suitable learning activities, apply instructional objectives, and overcome obstacles that arise. On the other hand, the teacher candidates get better at providing feedback, measuring, and evaluating during learner learning. Additionally, kids get the opportunity to see and assess various teaching methods by watching their friends' presentations (Abdurrahman, 2010). Micro-teaching, as defined by Ajayi in Cuthbert (2017), is a system of controlled practice that allows student-teachers to focus on particular teaching practices and is a requirement for several educational courses, such as Teaching Practice for Education students. An essential part of teacher preparation is teaching practice. It provides student-instructors with hands-on experience in a real teaching and learning setting. However, during learner learning, the teacher candidates improve their ability to measure, evaluate, and give feedback. Additionally, by observing their classmates' presentations, children get the chance to observe and evaluate a variety of instructional strategies (Abdurrahman, 2010).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Given that the teacher is seen as both the learner's "everything" and the society's role model, it is anticipated that his instruction be both thorough and clearly understood. Solid conceptual knowledge and reasoning that have been developed within the framework of high-quality educational experiences and practices, such as microteaching, must serve as the foundation for such training. However, the equipment used in this microteaching approach is too costly and difficult to supply in sufficient quantities to teacher education institutions that require it. Purchasing, installing, and maintaining educational institutions' accessories is becoming more and more challenging in Nigeria's current economic climate. The Federal Government (FRN, 2014) suggested that concerned professionals start working on the creation and efficient application of

low-cost alternative methods for microteaching and assessment. For many years, teacher educators around the world have been considering how to best prepare trainees to become effective classroom practitioners (Gorge, 2010).

According to an analysis of the literature on teacher education and classroom practice, little is currently understood about how students' teacher education and training, more especially, microteaching affect their practices (Alhassan, 2012). In light of this, the researcher wants to determine the true impact of microteaching by analyzing the performance of student teachers in vocational and technical education during their teaching practicum in Abia State.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The main purpose of this study was to examine the micro teaching impact on Vocational and Technical Education student-teachers' performance during teaching practice in Abia State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. examine the impact of microteaching in preparing Vocational and Technical Education student-teachers in teaching VTE subjects during teaching practices in Abia State.
2. determine the impact of microteaching in improving Vocational and Technical Education student-teachers' classroom confidence during teaching practices in Abia State.
3. find out the impact of microteaching in motivating Vocational and Technical Education student-teachers in becoming professional teachers of VTE.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions guided this research work:

1. What is the impact of microteaching in preparing Vocational and Technical Education student-teachers in teaching VTE subjects during teaching practices in Abia State?
2. What is the impact of microteaching in improving Vocational and Technical Education student-teachers' classroom confidence during teaching practices in Abia State?
3. What is the impact of microteaching in motivating Vocational and Technical Education student-teachers in becoming professional teachers of VTE?

RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

The null hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

HO₁: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female VTE students on the impact of microteaching in motivating Vocational and Technical Education student-teachers in becoming professional teachers of VTE in Abia State.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Historical Background of Microteaching

Microteaching is one of the innovations used to improve teacher education. According to Adeleke (2011), microteaching is a scaled-down teaching encounter in which the teacher trainee teaches 10 students instead of 45–55 students in a normal class, spends 5–10 minutes in a normal class instead of 40 minutes, practices one skill at a time instead of using many integrated skills in a normal lesson, and has only one or two objectives from the content instead of having roughly four or five objectives for a normal lesson. For instance, Singh (2011) reports that children in the United States performed poorly and unsatisfactorily academically in the 1950s and 1960s. While teachers stated they were not given the teaching and learning

skills they needed to achieve and meet societal expectations, they were also held accountable for using subpar teaching practices. This called for experimentation on the experiences which could be relevant for teaching in terms of new teacher practice programs by educators. As a result, governments and foundations like Ford & Kettering provided significant financing for a number of technologies. One group that benefited from this financial assistance was the University of Stanford group that created microteaching. An earlier introduction to microteaching was used at the start. At Stanford University, it was the direct forerunner of microteaching (Audu, 2010). While the rest of the class watched, a teacher candidate gave a lesson to a small group of other student teachers during the teacher training demonstration period. It was from this sample lesson that microteaching eventually evolved by 1963.

According to Bakir (2014), who wrote about the history of microteaching, the term was first used at Stanford University in the United States of America during an experimental project on the identification of teaching skills that was being carried out under the direction and supervision of faculty members Bush, Allen, McDonald, and Acheson. The construction of testing and evaluation instruments to gauge the completion of teaching experiences that would be pertinent to teaching interns in a cutting-edge teacher education programme was given to the team of specialists. The group started a new laboratory experience and method for teacher preparation under the Secondary Teacher Education Programme (STEP) umbrella. The program's original name was "Demonstration Teaching." Through fieldwork and research, the qualities that could make a teacher effective were determined during the approach's development. The items on the list were thought to be teachable, learnable, and capable of transforming behaviour in the intended ways. Thus, the idea of "teaching skills" developed. Furthermore, Ghanaguru et al. (2013) linked the development of video technology in Germany to the origins of microteaching worldwide. They noted that Stanford University's Keith Acheson, N.B. Robert, and W. Allen Dwight were responsible for microteaching. They also agreed with Chuanjan and Chummei (2011) that the development of microteaching was boosted and supported by Ford Foundation. They noted that, in accordance with Obilom (2008), microteaching was first known as demonstration teaching. Later, microteaching was established and regarded as an excellent teacher training tool notably at the pre-service level. The stages of microteaching, such as harmattan fire, spread from the United States of America (USA) to countries like Malaysia, the United Kingdom, and Australia between the 1970s and 1980s. In the 1990s, microteaching was widely recognised as a crucial strategy and a cure-all for effective teacher training, but Nigeria was not left behind.

Objectives and Nature of Microteaching

Teacher education is a vital training that is aimed for instructors and teaching profession. Practice is one of the main elements of a teacher education programme. Prior teacher candidates receive microteaching to provide them the teaching abilities they need before being placed in a regular classroom for practice. Audu (2010) asserts that skill acquisition in the classroom is one of the persistent issues in teacher education. Microteaching exposes preservice teachers to the fundamentals of teaching. Three phases were identified by Eze (2013) and Aarsal (2013) in their writings on the phases of microteaching: the knowledge acquisition phase, the skill acquisition phase, and the transfer phase. The first phase, known as the knowledge acquisition phase, is referred to as the proactive phase. During this phase, pre-service teachers are taught the skills and their components through lectures, tutorials, illustrations, orientation, and expert demonstrations. They also learn about the purpose of the skill and the conditions under which it proves useful in the teaching-learning process. The second phase is the acquisition phase, which is described as an interactive phase where teacher trainees are expected to plan a micro-lesson based on the expert demonstration (Bakir, 2014).

Through the microteaching cycle, teacher candidates practice the skills until they reach the mastery level, and the feedback component of microteaching plays a significant role in helping them reach the mastery level. The final phase is the transfer stage, also known as the post-active phase, where the student teacher integrates all of the skills and moves on to actual classroom instruction. Ismail (2011) states that one of the main goals of microteaching is to allow teacher candidates to acquire and assimilate new teaching skills in a controlled environment or conditions. Pre-service teachers can learn a variety of teaching techniques through microteaching, which gives them more confidence in their ability to instruct. "You cannot learn to swim if you do not get in the water," goes a well-known proverb. According to the same school of thought, microteaching is designed to provide teacher candidates the tools they need to become more confident educators (Obilom, 2008). It accomplishes this by requiring the pre-service teachers to become proficient in a variety of abilities with a small group of pupils. Furthermore, Higgins and Nicholl (2003) contend that the goal of microteaching is to support teacher candidates in developing their research abilities and self-assurance. Pre-service teachers can develop their academic confidence and pre-service and in-service teaching experiences through microteaching. Pre-service teachers must utilise a specific teaching ability for a brief period of time, teach a particular topic, and employ the skill on a very small number of students, even though microteaching has certain features. According to Garba (2017), microteaching is a real teaching scenario in which the intricacy of traditional classroom instruction is diminished. The reduction is done in terms of time (duration), class size (population) and substance (job to be achieved). Instead of dealing with the actual classroom setting of roughly 45 to 50 kids, teacher candidates who are considered micro-teachers instruct 5–10 pupils who are probably their classmates, acquaintances, coworkers, and fellow students. The micro teachers create their lesson plan and teach for no more than ten (10) minutes, as opposed to the forty-five to fifty minutes that are typical in a real classroom. Additionally, the job at hand is condensed to one or two instructional objectives due to the reduction in both population and time.

As a result, microteaching gives student teachers the opportunity to teach in a fear-free environment. Until students become proficient in applying the learned skill, they repeatedly practice the teaching skill in situations that are defined, observable, measurable, and controllable situation with repeated cycles till they attain mastery in the use of acquired skill.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey research design and it was considered suitable because the opinion of a representative sample of respondents was sought using questionnaire and the finding was generalized on the entire population. The target population consisted of 1345 Vocational and Technical Education students drafted from the 2 Public Universities in Abia state, Nigeria (i.e - MOUAU and ABSU). However, there is no department of Technical and Vocational Education (TVET) being run in the Universities located in area of the study, nevertheless the programmes of TVET exist in the area of study: Agricultural Education, Business Education, and Home Economics Education. Additionally, the sample size was 299 respondents, determined using Taro's Yamene Formula. The instrument for data collection was questionnaire titled: Impact of Micro teaching Questionnaire (IMTQ). The questionnaire was developed from literature by the researchers and used for data collection. The instrument was a four point response scale of strongly agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly disagreed (SD) with corresponding values of 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. The instrument was face – validated by three experts: Two from Department of Agricultural and Home Science Education- Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike and one from Measurement and Evaluation Department- Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike. Their corrections and suggestions were utilized to improve the initial copies of the questionnaire to produce the final copies. Cronbach Alpha reliability method was adopted to determine the internal consistency of the questionnaire items. A Cronbach

Alpha coefficient of 0.82 was obtained and the collected data was analyzed using mean for research questions and t-test for the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Any mean response of 2.50 and above was considered agreed while any mean response below 2.50 was considered disagreed.

RESULTS

Research Question 1

What is the impact of microteaching in preparing Vocational and Technical Education student-teachers in teaching VTE subjects during teaching practices in Abia State?

Table 1: Mean rating of the responses of respondents on the impact of microteaching in preparing Vocational and Technical Education student-teachers in teaching VTE subjects during teaching practices
n = 299

S/N	Item statement	\bar{x}	SD	Rmk
1.	Microteaching boosts students' class management skills	3.31	.73	Agreed
2.	Microteaching helps student-teachers in developing their confidence before teaching practice	3.40	.64	Agreed
3.	Microteaching helps the student-teacher in developing time management skill	3.39	.63	Agreed
4.	Microteaching builds teaching skills and styles in student-teachers	3.31	.73	Agreed
5.	Microteaching helps to improve student-teachers' white board writing skills	3.28	.70	Agreed
6.	Microteaching prepares students for effective use of instructional materials	3.26	.68	Agreed
7.	Microteaching helps students to present classroom instructions logically and sequentially	3.24	.76	Agreed
8	Microteaching helps to boost students' mastery of the subject matter	3.28	.70	Agreed
9	Microteaching helps students in identifying areas for improvement in teaching	3.13	.80	Agreed

SD = Standard Deviation of the respondents and \bar{X} = Mean of the respondents

Data in Table 1 revealed that all the 9 items had their mean ratings ranging from 3.13 to 3.40 and were above the cut-off point of 2.50. This indicated that the respondents agreed that microteaching positively impact on Vocational and Technical education student teachers in preparing for effective teaching of VTE subjects during teaching practices in Abia State. The standard deviation of all the 9 items ranged from .63 to .80, which showed that the respondents were not too far from the mean and opinion of one another in their responses on the impact of microteaching in preparing Vocational and Technical Education student-teachers in teaching VTE subjects during teaching practices in Abia State.

Research Question 2

What is the impact of microteaching in improving Vocational and Technical Education student-teachers' classroom confidence during teaching practices in Abia State?

Table 2: Mean rating of the responses of respondents on the impact of microteaching in improving Vocational and Technical Education student-teachers' classroom confidence during teaching practices
n = 299

S/N	Item statements	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Student teachers are motivated to become professional teachers through the development of class management skills during micro teaching	3.14	.79	Agreed
2	Microteaching motivates student teacher to become professionals due to the feedback from students during evaluation	3.13	.80	Agreed

3	The use of appropriate instructional materials motivates student teachers to become professionals	3.14	.79	Agreed
4	The planning of the lesson before teaching practice motivates student teachers to become professional	3.14	.79	Agreed
5	Microteaching helps boost students' interest in the teaching profession	3.34	.77	Agreed
6	Microteaching makes students to dislike the teaching profession	2.84	.87	Agreed
7	Microteaching helps students to acquire appropriate dress sense as a professional teacher	3.13	.80	Agreed
8	Microteaching helps to provide valuable feedback for ensuring effective and efficient teaching profession	3.26	.68	Agreed
9	I feel more confidence in taking up teaching as my profession in life on graduation because of micro teaching experiences.	3.24	.76	Agreed

SD = Standard Deviation of the respondents and \bar{X} = Mean of the respondents

Data in Table 2 revealed that all the 9 items had their mean ratings ranging from 2.84 to 3.34 and were above the cut-off point of 2.50. This indicated that the respondents agreed that microteaching helps in improving Vocational and Technical Education student-teachers' classroom confidence during teaching practices in Abia State. The standard deviation of all the 9 items ranged from .68 to .87, which showed that the respondents were not too far from the mean and opinion of one another in their responses on the impact of microteaching in improving Vocational and Technical Education student-teachers' classroom confidence during teaching practices in Abia State.

Research Question 3

What is the impact of microteaching in motivating Vocational and Technical Education student-teachers in becoming professional teachers of VTE?

Table 3: Mean rating of the responses of respondents on impact of microteaching in motivating Vocational and Technical Education student-teachers in becoming professional teachers of VTE n = 299

S/N	Item statements	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Microteaching has helped me develop a more positive self-image.	2.65	.48	Agreed
2	I am more confident in my public speaking skills after microteaching.	2.72	.50	Agreed
3	Practicing microteaching has boosted my self-assurance in teaching.	2.95	.85	Agreed
4	I feel more confident in my ability to handle challenging situations.	2.60	.49	Agreed
5	Microteaching has improved my overall confidence level.	2.63	.58	Agreed
6	I believe microteaching has helped me overcome my fears and doubts.	3.18	.83	Agreed
7	I feel more empowered and confident in my teaching abilities.	3.17	.76	Agreed
8	Microteaching has enhanced my confidence in expressing my ideas.	2.65	.48	Agreed
9	I am more likely to take on new challenges with confidence after microteaching	2.72	.50	Agreed

SD = Standard Deviation of the respondents and \bar{X} = Mean of the respondents

Data in Table 3 revealed that all the 9 items had their mean ratings ranging from 2.60 to 3.18 and were above the cut-off point of 2.50. This indicated that the respondents agreed that microteaching helps in motivating Vocational and Technical education student teachers in becoming professional teachers of VTE. The standard deviation of all the 9 items ranged from .48 to .85, which showed that the respondents were not too far from the mean and opinion of one another in their responses on the impact of microteaching in motivating Vocational and Technical education student teachers in becoming professional teachers of VTE.

Hypothesis one

HO₁: There is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female VTE students on the impact of microteaching in motivating Vocational and Technical Education student-teachers in becoming professional teachers of VTE in Abia State.

Table 4: t-test analysis of mean difference between male and female VTE students on the impact of microteaching in motivating Vocational and Technical Education student-teachers in becoming professional teachers

Gender	N	X	SD	Df	t-cal	α	Sig.	Decision
Male	192	2.89	.61	297	1.22	0.05	.063	Accepted H ₀₁
Female	107	2.70	.52					

Source: t-test Result from SPSS

Data on table 4 shows that t-cal of 1.22 is less than the t-crit of 1.67 at 0.05 level of significance, which indicates that the hypothesis stated is accepted. This means there is no significant difference between the mean responses of male and female VTE students on the impact of microteaching in motivating Vocational and Technical Education student-teachers in becoming professional teachers of VTE in Abia State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The data presented in table 1 above revealed that all the 9 items had their mean ratings above the cut-off point of 2.50. This indicated that the respondents agreed that microteaching positively impact on Vocational and Technical education student teachers in preparing teaching of VTE subjects during teaching practices in Abia state. The findings is in line with Oguntunde (2019) who stated that microteaching expresses student teachers to the realities of teaching. It introduces them to their roles as teachers and enables them to realize the difficulties faced by teachers especially in Nigerian classroom. In addition, it conforms with Afolabi (2010) who noted that microteaching affords student teachers the opportunity to gain competency in writing lesson plans, stating objectives and delivering their lessons.

In table 2, the study revealed that all the 9 items had their mean ratings above the cut-off point of 2.50. This indicated that the respondents agreed that microteaching helps in improving Vocational and Technical education student teachers' classroom confidence during teaching practices in Abia state. The findings was in agreement with Achuonye in Ajileye (2012) who noted that student-teachers are given opportunity to overcome mannerism, nervousness and other semantic barriers which can hinder their performance before the audience and supervisors. Also, the findings agreed with the result of Ismail (2010) who stated that micro teaching enhances teacher confidence and competence by providing opportunity for practice, feedback and reflection. The author concluded by saying that claimed that when microteaching is properly carried

out, the teaching practice exercise is likely to be a more rewarding and successful exercise and it is because increase in the number of weeks spent for teaching practice by student teachers cannot compensate for weak campus based practical trainings.

Findings on research question 3 revealed that all the 9 items had their mean ratings above the cut-off point of 2.50. This indicated that the respondents agreed that microteaching helps in motivating Vocational and Technical education student teachers in becoming professional teachers of VTE. The findings was in agreement with Kilic (2010) who submitted that micro teaching experiences significantly improve pre-service teachers' self – efficacy beliefs and confidence in their teaching abilities, preparing them for the teaching profession. Furthermore, it connotes with the result of Adewoyin (2017) and Ajibade (2019) who revealed that microteaching makes student teachers concentrate on specific teaching behaviours to becoming a good teacher. The authors concluded by stated that they choose and master a skill at a time and that it is after mastering a skill that they choose another one until they are able to master and integrate all the microteaching skills in real time teachings.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings and discussion of the findings, it can be concluded that micro teaching has a major effect on the performance of Vocational and Technical Education Student Teachers during Teaching Practice by building up their confidence, time management skills, teaching skills and style, and has motivated them to become professionals in their field. Also, it can be inferred that the use of appropriate instructional materials during micro teaching has benefited in the development of student-teachers skills. Additionally, it found that microteaching helped undergraduate technical and vocational students improve their teaching abilities and lower their levels of fear and anxiety, Proficiency in class management, appropriate teaching goal selection, lesson planning, public speaking, appropriate instructional material selection, and time management all contributed to an improvement in teaching practice performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. The Instructors/lecturers of micro teaching should give appropriate attention to the method in which micro teaching is carried out, in order to ensure quality of lesson delivery.
2. The government should allocate sufficient funds to support the ongoing advancement of microteaching in Nigerian university faculties and colleges of education.
3. More time should be allotted for micro teaching so that supervisors of micro teaching can observe, criticize and give encouraging comments to micro teachers before they are exposed to teaching practice.
4. Microteaching supervisors and instructors should make sure that micro teachers engage in positive ways by helping them realize the value of microteaching to them, not just for grades.

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